

Synthesis and Fungitoxicity of Some 4-Substituted 2-Amino-(Halogeno)nitrophenyl-Thiazoles

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Thirty four 4-substituted-2-amino-halogenonitrophenyl thiazoles have been prepared by the condensation of halogenonitrobenzenes and 2-amino-4-methyl and 2-amino-4-phenyl thiazoles. They have been characterised and tested for their antifungal activity against *Helminthosporium sativum*, *Alternaria tenuis*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Fusarium oxysporum* by spore germination method. A relation between fungitoxicity and structure has also been established.

THIAZOLE derivatives were found to be active against smut and bunt of wheat, carnation rust, mildew on leather and textiles and mycoses of humans^{1,2}. 2,4-Di-substituted thiazoles have also exhibited local anaesthetic action and antihistaminic activity³. The presence of lipophilic and polar substituents like aryl and amino groups in the thiazole nucleus are expected to enhance the fungitoxic property⁴. 2-Amino-4-aryl thiazole and their derivatives impart antibacterial⁵ and fungicidal activity⁶. In view of the wide range of fungicidal activity of these compounds, it was considered of interest to synthesise few 4-substituted-2-aminohalogenonitrophenyl thiazoles carrying halogen, nitro and methyl groups at different positions in the phenyl ring and to test their fungicidal activity.

4-substituted-2-amino-halogenonitrophenyl thiazoles (III) as detailed in Table 1 and 2 have been obtained by the condensation of halogenonitrobenzene(II) with 2-amino-4-substituted thiazoles(I) in ethanolic solution in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate. The I.R. spectra of these compounds are recorded and are in complete agreement with their structures.

These compounds were tested for their antifungal activity against *Helminthosporium sativum*, *Alternaria tenuis*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Fusarium oxysporum* by spore germination method⁷ (Table 1 and 2). The percentage inhibition of spores at 10 ppm have been recorded.

Structure of Some 4-substituted-2-amino-halogenonitrophenyl thiazoles :

Structures of the thiazoles obtained from 1,2,5-trihalogeno-4,6-dinitrobenzene, which has two labile halogen atoms in position 1 and 5, follow from the previous observation⁸ that it is the halogen atom at position-1 which takes part in the condensation. Thus 1,2,5-trichloro- (or 2,5-dichloro-1-bromo-)4,6-dinitrobenzene gave 4-substituted-2-amino-(2,5-dichloro-4,6-dinitrophenyl)-thiazole when condensed with 2-amino-4-substituted thiazoles.

Similarly 1,2,5-tribromo- and 1-chloro-2,5-dibromo-4,6-dinitrobenzene furnished identical products, and proved to be 4-substituted-2-amino-(2,5-dibromo-4,6-dinitrophenyl)-thiazole.

Experimental

4-Substituted-2-amino-halogenonitrophenyl-thiazoles :

A solution of halogenonitrobenzene (0.01 mol) in absolute alcohol (15-20 ml.) was added dropwise to a solution of 2-amino-4-substituted-thiazole^{9,10} (0.01 mol.) in absolute alcohol (20.0 ml.), with constant stirring. The mixture was refluxed on a waterbath for about two to three hours in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate. The mixture was filtered off and cooled. The product was washed with water and recrystallised from alcohol.

The thiazole derivatives so prepared are insoluble in water and are completely soluble in alcohol. Their melting points, yield, analytical data and fungitoxicity have been recorded in Table 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—4-METHYL-2-AMINO-(HALOGENO)NITROPHENYL-THIAZOLES

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	% Nitrogen		% Sulphur		Percentage inhibition of spores at 10 ppm			
					Found	Reqd	Found	Reqd.	HS	AT	AN	FO
1.	2,4-DNP	81	95	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ O ₄ S	19.95	20.00	11.41	11.43	30	23	28	36
2.	2,6-DNP	85	92	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ O ₄ S	19.97	20.00	11.40	11.43	35	26	35	45
3.	2,4,6-TNP	190	92	C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₅ O ₆ S	21.52	21.54	9.83	9.84	38	30	30	28
4.	2-Chloro-4,6-DNP	178	88	C ₁₀ H ₇ ClN ₄ O ₄ S	17.80	17.80	10.20	10.17	32	45	46	25
5.	2-Bromo-4,6-DNP	185	90	C ₁₀ H ₇ BrN ₄ O ₄ S	15.60	15.59	8.87	8.91	40	36	40	38
6.	3-Chloro-4,6-DNP	86	95	C ₁₀ H ₇ ClN ₄ O ₄ S	17.84	17.80	10.13	19.17	29	36	25	20
7.	4-Chloro-2,6-DNP	105	85	C ₁₀ H ₇ ClN ₄ O ₄ S	17.80	17.80	10.16	10.17	36	35	23	00
8.	2-Methyl-4,6-DNP	70	96	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₄ S	19.02	19.05	10.91	10.88	26	20	16	00
9.	4-Methyl-2,6-DNP	98	78	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₄ S	19.04	19.05	10.87	10.88	26	28	20	00
10.	3-Methyl-2,4,6-TNP	128	80	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₅ O ₆ S	20.66	20.65	9.43	9.44	8	8	8	00
11.	2,3-Dichloro-4,6-DNP	215	96	C ₁₀ H ₆ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₄ S	16.00	16.04	9.12	9.17	42	42	28	44
12.	2,5-Dichloro-4,6-DNP	108	92	C ₁₀ H ₆ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₄ S	16.03	16.04	9.10	9.17	50	40	23	30
13.	2,5-Dibromo-4,6-DNP	118	85	C ₁₀ H ₆ Br ₂ N ₄ O ₄ S	10.80	12.78	7.26	7.39	32	28	20	28
14.	2-Chloro-3-bromo-4,6-DNP	135	80	C ₁₀ H ₆ ClBrN ₄ O ₄ S	14.18	14.23	8.14	8.13	4	00	00	00
15.	2-Chloro-5-methyl-4,6-DNP	110	85	C ₁₁ H ₉ ClN ₄ O ₄ S	17.00	17.04	9.72	9.74	40	15	10	00
16.	2-Bromo-5-methyl-4,6-DNP	125	85	C ₁₁ H ₉ BrN ₄ O ₄ S	14.95	15.01	8.51	8.58	32	15	8	00
17.	3-Chloro-2-methyl-4,6-DNP	120	90	C ₁₁ H ₉ ClN ₄ O ₄ S	16.98	17.04	9.13	9.74	38	32	23	32

TABLE 2—4-PHENYL-2-AMINO-(HALOGENO)NITROPHENYL-THIAZOLES

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	% Nitrogen		% Sulphur		Percentage inhibition of spores at 10 ppm			
					Found	Reqd	Found	Reqd	HS	AT	AN	FO
1.	2,4-DNP	95	96	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₄ S	16.28	16.37	9.33	9.35	35	38	31	36
2.	2,6-DNP	81	95	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₄ S	16.34	16.37	9.36	9.35	38	30	34	47
3.	2,4,6-TNP	130	90	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₅ O ₆ S	18.10	18.01	8.22	8.26	44	24	40	34
4.	2-Chloro-4,6-DNP	175	95	C ₁₅ H ₉ ClN ₄ O ₄ S	14.83	14.87	8.51	8.49	36	36	46	30
5.	2-Bromo-4,6-DNP	140	92	C ₁₅ H ₉ BrN ₄ O ₄ S	13.24	13.30	7.54	7.60	42	45	42	42
6.	3-Chloro-4,6-DNP	90	88	C ₁₅ H ₉ ClN ₄ O ₄ S	14.89	14.87	8.39	8.49	28	36	30	18

Table 2 (Contd.)

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield	Mol. Formula	% Nitrogen		% Sulphur		Percentage inhibition of spores at 10 ppm			
					Found	Reqd	Found	Reqd	HS	AT	AN	FO
7.	4-Chloro-2,6-DNP	95	80	C ₁₅ H ₉ ClN ₄ O ₄ S	14.86	14.87	8.42	8.49	32	35	34	30
8.	2-Methyl-4,6-DNP	68	95	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₄ S	15.71	15.73	8.97	8.98	25	22	17	20
9.	4-Methyl-2,6-DNP	92	85	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₄ S	15.70	15.73	8.95	8.98	10	20	12	00
10.	3-Methyl-2,4,6-TNP	128	82	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₆ O ₆ S	17.38	17.45	7.92	7.98	8	10	10	5
11.	2,3-Dichloro-4,6-DNP	220	90	C ₁₅ H ₈ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₄ S	13.52	13.62	7.80	7.78	48	32	20	10
12.	2,5-Dichloro-4,6-DNP	125	88	C ₁₅ H ₈ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₄ S	13.63	13.62	7.65	7.78	55	34	23	23
13.	2,5-Dibromo-4,6-DNP	148	80	C ₁₅ H ₈ Br ₂ N ₄ O ₄ S	11.14	11.20	6.38	6.40	35	30	28	20
14.	2-Chloro-3-Bromo-4,6-DNP	100	78	C ₁₅ H ₈ ClBrN ₄ O ₄ S	12.25	12.29	7.00	7.02	5	6	18	0
15.	2-Chloro-5-methyl-4,6-DNP	87	90	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClN ₄ O ₄ S	14.35	14.34	8.16	8.19	32	18	26	0
16.	2-Bromo-5-methyl-4,6-DNP	120	85	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ BrN ₄ O ₄ S	12.84	12.87	7.38	7.35	28	20	20	0
17.	3-Chloro-2-methyl-4,6-DNP	105	95	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClN ₄ O ₄ S	14.34	14.34	8.15	8.19	26	35	26	16

DNP and TNP refers to dinitro— and trinitrophenyl respectively. All melting points are uncorrected. Satisfactory C, H analysis have been obtained for all these compounds.

HS, AT, AN and FO refers to *Helminthosporium sativum*, *Alternaria tenuis*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Fusarium oxysporum* respectively.

Results and Discussion

The fungitoxicity of 4-substituted-2-amino-halogeno-nitrophenyl thiazoles depends on both, the thiazole ring as well as the phenyl ring. The fungitoxicity sharply increases with the number of nitro groups at ortho and para positions in phenyl ring. Similarly a halogen atom increases fungitoxicity when placed at ortho or para position in phenyl ring. However, a halogen atom at meta position exhibits relatively weak fungitoxicity. When methyl group is present in phenyl ring in ortho, meta or para position, it decreases fungitoxicity.

In the thiazole ring, phenyl substituent at 4th position increases the fungitoxicity in comparison to methyl group.

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